

Frequency Scanning Antenna Concept with Random Feed Lengths

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Introduction

Moving target indicator (MTI) radars have been used to detect and track targets since World War II. Historically, radar search was performed by rotating an antenna on a gimbal [1]. More recently, radar search is performed electronically by scanning with a phased array antenna that uses switches, ferroelectric, or other active devices. Electronically scanned antennas can be expensive and consume large amounts of power. One technique to reduce the number of elements, and therefore the cost, is to use aperiodic placement of antenna elements [2]. This has been shown to have an acceptable impact on performance metrics such as sidelobe level [3]. I am proposing a similar technique for antenna design: use temporal diversity rather than, or potentially in addition to, spatial diversity to reduce cost. This idea can be implemented using a frequency scanning antenna with random length delay lines in combination with digital signal processing algorithms. Traditional frequency scanning antennas have poor range resolution [4]. The goal of this design is to have the range resolution proportional to the transmit bandwidth and to be capable of searching for targets in all directions simultaneously. The major disadvantages of the concept are the signal processing is much more complicated, the gain of the antenna may be reduced relative to a similar sized antenna, and there are potential ambiguities associated with target localization. The proposed radar system has a simple radar RF design, an antenna with no active elements, and a data acquisition system comprised of a single slow-speed analog-to-digital converter (ADC). This paper will examine the feasibility of a 1-D design for estimating the azimuth angle for stationary targets and the position and velocity of moving targets.

RF hardware

To simplify the RF architecture and signal processing, a radar system based upon CW stepped-frequency waveform is proposed. Fig. 1 shows a block diagram of the RF hardware. The signal is transmitted through a single antenna and received with an array of antennas that are combined with feed lines of random length. The received signal is amplified, down converted, then smoothed with a band pass filter (BPF). Only signals from moving targets will pass to the ADC.

Conceptually, the proposed radar system contains enough information to track moving targets in stationary clutter. The velocity of the targets can be determined by performing a discrete Fourier transform (DFT) on the time samples collected at each frequency. Conceptually, the range information on moving targets can be obtained by performing a DFT across the Doppler processed results. This technique does not work in practice for the described hardware because of aliasing, quadratic errors, and large amplitude modulations on the Doppler processed data. Conceptually, the angle of the targets can be determined using techniques such as matched filter processing or least squares estimation. To realize these concepts, stochastic optimization techniques need to be

developed to simultaneously estimate these target parameters. We will study the feasibility of minimizing a cost function based upon the Euclidian norm.

Figure 1 Block diagram of radar system.

Simulation Results

1-D antenna patterns were simulated using matched filters and a weighted least squares approach (WLSQ) [5]. Simulations were performed with the following parameters: carrier frequency of 10 GHz, bandwidth of 1 GHz, 64 frequency steps, 64 antenna elements, and $\lambda/2$ antenna element spacing with Gaussian beam patterns centered at broadside with 1-way 3 dB beamwidths of 120 degrees. The matrices required for the WLSQ fit were generated by sampling the antenna response in angle every $\pi/512$ radians and the matrix inverse was computed in Matlab using the pseudo inverse function. The results are shown in fig 2. The red curve shows the results for a WLSQ fit to the desired antenna pattern shown by the blue curve, and the black curve is generated using conventional or a matched filter approach. As expected, the sidelobes are high.

Figure 2 Simulated 1-D antenna pattern using conventional and WLSQ approach.

To reduce the sidelobes, the estimated signal strength at a given angle can be calculated using coefficients calculated at a desired angle that include the additional constraint of a null at a selected angle. The beam pattern is determined by varying the null angle, then keeping the minimum output signal for an array of beam patterns at each angle as shown below

$$Y(\theta) = \min |w_j^H V(\theta)|, \quad j = 1 \dots J. \quad (1)$$

where w_j are the coefficients calculated for an array of null angles indexed by j , $v(\theta)$ is a $M \times 1$ array manifold vector for a given angle that is a function of frequency step number rather than element number [6].

1-D antenna patterns were simulated for signal-to-noise ratios (SNR) of 10, 20, and 25 dB as shown in fig. 3. The SNRs were calculated for a single antenna element. The array of null angles went from $-\pi/2$ to $\pi/2$ in $\pi/256$ increments, with the region at the desired angle $\pm \pi/128$ excluded. The antenna patterns were calculated at angles going from $-\pi/2$ to $\pi/2$ in $\pi/256$ increments, but were offset by $\pi/512$.

Figure 3. 1-D antenna patterns were simulated for SNR of 10, 20, and 25 dB.

The simulation results indicate that reasonable 1-D patterns can be generated for stationary targets. The sidelobe levels in the 1-D patterns improve as the number of elements and the fractional bandwidth is increased. The performance also improved as the number of frequencies is increased, but levels off as it approaches the number of antenna elements. For the parameters selected, reasonable sidelobe levels required a relatively high SNR.

The advantage of this antenna concept compared to traditional frequency scanning antennas is the ability to estimate range with resolution proportional to bandwidth. A disadvantage of this antenna is the processing required to estimate target parameters such as range is a nonlinear optimization problem. One possible formulation of the problem is to minimize the Euclidian or L_2 -norm of the cost function given by

$$\min(A_i, \bar{x}_i, \bar{v}_i, \phi_i) \left\{ \left\| D(n, k) - \sum_{i=1}^I (\hat{D}(n, k, A_i, \bar{x}_i, \bar{v}_i, \phi_i)) \right\| \right\} \quad (2)$$

where A_i is the amplitude of the i th scattering center, \bar{x}_i is the position of the i th scattering center, \bar{v}_i is the velocity of the i th scattering center, ϕ_i is the phase of the i th

scattering center, I is the total number of target scattering centers, $D(n,k)$ is the DFT of the measured data, n is the frequency step, k is the Doppler bin, and $\hat{D}(n,k,A_i,\bar{x}_i,\bar{v}_i,\phi_i)$ is the predicted value of $D(n,k)$. This is a complicated optimization problem, but for most applications, the number of targets in each Doppler bin should be zero or one, and for many applications there is only one or a few scattering centers per target. A 2-D slice of the cost function is plotted for a target located at (25,15) m as a function of position, while the other parameters were fixed at their correct values.

Figure 4 Cost function for a single target located at (25,10) m.

Conclusions

A block diagram of a radar architecture to support a frequency scanning antenna with random length feed lines was developed. The feasibility of the architecture to perform target localization in position and velocity was investigated by analyzing 1-d antenna patterns and costs functions based upon an L_2 -norm. A large trade space exists between adding complexity to the radar system versus simplifying the signal processing. For this paper, a single realization of the system was selected, then simulated. The results indicate that the concept is feasible, but requires high SNR and a small number of targets for unambiguous results. This concept can be extended from a single array to multiple subarrays for improved performance and to reduced requirements on the delay line lengths and the percent bandwidth of the system with the cost of additional data acquisition hardware and increased computational complexity.

References

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